

Additional information to Research Letter

Diet diversity in pregnancy and early allergic manifestations in the offspring

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Additional information	Description	Page
Methods	Comprehensive information about the study population and methods used in the study	1-3
Fig 1	Flow chart of inclusion and exclusion of study participants	4
Table 1	List of foods included in the diet diversity score and description on how the score was calculated	5
Table 2	Data on the frequency of consumption or mean intake of the food items included in the DD score	6
Table 3	Additional results showing sensitivity analyses of the association between DD score in pregnancy and allergic manifestations until the age of 18 months presenting multivariable odds ratios additionally adjusted for post-natal factors	7

Methods

Study population and study participants

We used data from the large population-based NorthPop Birth Cohort Study implemented in the county of Västerbotten in Northern Sweden (1), with the overall aim of collecting longitudinal data to study the early life environment in relation to subsequent disease and health status. Since 2016, pregnant women in Västerbotten are together with their partner invited to participate in the birth cohort study at their routine ultra sound examination at gestational week 17-20. The families are prospectively followed until the child is 7 years old with repeated web-based questionnaires and biological samples being collected during these years.

Inclusion and exclusion of study participants in this study are presented in **Fig 1**. After exclusions, 3200 mother-child dyads constituted the total study population. The study is reported in accordance with Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology and nutrition (STROBE-Nut) guidelines for observational studies.

Dietary data in pregnancy and calculation of a diet diversity score

Dietary data were collected from the pregnant women through a web based self-reported food frequency questionnaire (FFQ) sent out at pregnancy week 35. The FFQ included 125 food items for which the majority were reported in five different frequencies: never or rarely, 1-3 times/week, 4-6 times/week, 1-2 times/day, or ≥ 3 times/day. Beverages were reported in seven frequencies: never or rarely, 1-3 glasses/month, 1-3 glasses/week, 4-6 glasses/week, 1-2 glasses/day, 3-4 glasses/day, and ≥ 5 glasses/day, except milk and milk replacement for which participants reported the total amount/day consumed in deciliter (dl). For bread, slices/day were reported together with information on type of bread most often consumed. Participants were asked to rank consumed bread types from 1 (most often consumed) to a maximum of 6 (least often consumed).

A total of 40 food items were selected and used to calculate the diet diversity (DD) for the pregnant women (**Table 1**). The included foods were based on the EAACI taskforce recommendations for measuring diet diversity in the context of allergy (2) and on the present dietary guidelines for pregnant women in Sweden (3), covered by the questions in the FFQ. In brief, the recommendations during pregnancy are to eat plenty of vegetables and fruits (it is recommended to aim for 500 grams/day), to eat fish (both lean and fatty fish) and seafood 2-3 times/week, to use vegetable-based fat sources, to eat 3-5 dl of either milk, soured milk, yoghurt, or equivalent milk replacement products (preferably non-sweetened), and generally to keep a high variety in the diet (3).

For most items (n=33) in the constructed DD-score, each pregnant woman was assigned 1 point if she had reported to eat the food item 1-3 times/week or more and 0 points if less was reported. For red and white meat, 1 point was assigned if reported to be eaten between 1-3 times/week and 4-6 times/week. If fiber rich soft bread and fiber rich crisp bread, respectively, was reported as the most common bread type consumed (ranked as number 1 or 2 of 6 bread types), 1 point was assigned. If a total consumption of ≥ 2 dl milk or milk replacement per day was reported, 1 point was assigned. Finally, if consumption of unpasteurized milk was reported regularly, 1 point was assigned. Unpasteurized milk is recommended to not be consumed during pregnancy by the Swedish Food Agency due to the risk of bacterial infections caused by for example *Campylobacter* and *Listeria* (3) but was included in the DD-score based on research indicating that unpasteurized milk may protect against allergy development (4, 5). The DD-score could potentially range from 0-40 points for an individual and was adjusted for total energy intake in kcal per day during pregnancy using the residual method (6), because the DD-score was highly correlated with energy intake, and thus the adjusted DD-score became an estimate of the nutrient intake of diverse foods, uncorrelated with total energy intake.

Allergy outcomes in the offspring

The specific outcomes in this study were the cumulative incidence of parentally reported eczema (yes/no), wheeze (yes/no), physician diagnosed asthma (yes/no), and physician diagnosed FA (yes/no) until 18 months of age. In addition, eczema severity assessed by the Patient Oriented Eczema Measure (POEM)-score (0-28p), were reported. The POEM-scores were dichotomized into two groups based on five clinically used severity bands (7); 1. Score 0-7 (clear to mild eczema), and 2. Score 8-28 (moderate to very severe eczema).

At 18 months of age, the families were invited to an allergy screening test resulting in 60% participation rate of the children in this study. Collected blood samples were analyzed using the standardized ImmunoCAP method, Thermo Fisher Scientific Phadia, Uppsala, Sweden, according to the manufacturer's instructions at the Clinical Immunological Laboratory at Umeå University Hospital. The screening included an inhalation mix (Phadiatop) and a food mix (fx5) with cow's milk, egg white, wheat, peanuts, soy, and cod. Sensitization was defined as positive if IgE levels ≥ 0.35 PAU (Phadiatop) and 0.35 kUA/L (fx5).

Covariates

Data were collected through self-reported questionnaires, for factors regarding the mothers in gestational week 18-24, 26, 34, and 35 respectively, including for example occupation and educational level, medical history, household characteristics, and dietary habits. Questionnaires relating to the infants were collected at age 4-, 9-, and 18 months, respectively, and included information about health, medications and hospital visits, source of infant diet (breast milk or formula), and other eating habits. In addition, register data on gestational week of birth, age at delivery, delivery mode, child sex, height and weight of the infant, and information about neonatal care, were withdrawn from the Swedish pregnancy register and medical records.

Potential confounding factors related to the maternal diet and to the allergy outcomes of interest in the infant were considered and these were: gestational total daily energy intake, maternal history of allergy, maternal BMI at pregnancy registry, maternal education, gestational supplementation, delivery mode, child sex, breastfeeding duration, timing of solid food introduction, infant probiotic supplementation, and if there were other children/siblings in the household.

Statistical analyses

Associations between DD-score in pregnancy and cumulative incidence of allergic diseases were estimated using logistic regression for the outcomes eczema, wheeze, asthma, and FA, and multinomial logistic regression models were used for POEM-scores categorized into two groups (clear to mild- or moderate to severe eczema) with the group with no eczema constituting the reference group. Results are presented as energy adjusted odds ratios (ORs) and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) per 1 unit increase in DD-score and according to quartiles of the DD-score and in a multivariable model maternal history of allergy (no allergies, 1 allergy, 2-3 allergies, or ≥ 4 allergies), maternal BMI at pregnancy registration, and maternal education level (≤ 9 years elementary school, gymnasium/high school, or academic education), gestational supplementation of either; multivitamin, folic acid, omega3, or vitamin D (yes/no), delivery mode (vaginal/cesarean), and child sex (girl/boy). In a sensitivity test, the following post-natal factors were added to the first multivariable model: other children in the household (yes/no), breastfeeding duration until 18 months age (never breastfed, 0-3 months, 4-6 months, 7-9 months, 10-12 months, or ≥ 12 months), infant probiotic supplementation at 4 and 9 months respectively (yes/no), and timing of introduction to solid foods according to seven food categories in the infant (<6 or >6 months age). All statistical analyses were performed using the IBM SPSS Statistics v. 28.0 (IBM, New York, NY, USA) and a P-value of 0.05 was regarded as statistically significant.

Ethics

The study protocol for the present investigation was approved by the Regional Ethical Review Board, Umeå, Sweden, 2014/224-31. All participants (mother and partner) provided a written informed consent to use the collected data from both parent and child. All data handling complies with the European Union General Data Protection Regulation and the study conforms with the Code of Ethics of the World Medical Association (Declaration of Helsinki, 1964).

Figure 1. Inclusion and exclusion of mother-child dyads from the Northpop Birth Cohort in this study. *FFQ, food frequency questionnaire; kcal. kilocalorie*

Table 1. Included food items (n=40) in the diet diversity (DD) score in pregnant women in the Swedish NorthPop Birth Cohort Study. The DD-score was adjusted for total energy intake per day using the residual method (6)

Foods	Cutoff frequency or other measure	Foods	Cutoff frequency or other measure
Fiber rich foods:		Fruits & berries	
1 Fiber cereals	≥1-3 t/w = 1p	24 All fruits	1-2 t/day = 1p
2 Fiber porridge	≥1-3 t/w = 1p	25 All berries	≥1-3 t/w = 1p
Fiber rich bread		Meat	
3 Fiber pasta	≥1-3 t/w = 1p	26 Red meat	1-3 t/w to 4-6 t/w
4 Brown rice	≥1-3 t/w = 1p	27 White meat	1-3 t/w to 4-6 t/w
5 Bulgur/couscous/grain	≥1-3 t/w = 1p	Fish & seafood	
6 Fiber rich soft bread ^a	If most common bread = 1p	28 Fatty fish	≥1-3 t/w = 1p
7 Fiber rich crisp bread ^a	If most common bread = 1p	29 Lean fish	≥1-3 t/w = 1p
8 Boiled potatoes	≥1-3 t/w = 1p	30 Sea food	≥1-3 t/w = 1p
9 Carrots	≥1-3 t/w = 1p	31 Egg	≥1-3 t/w = 1p
10 Root vegetables	≥1-3 t/w = 1p	32 Pulses	≥1-3 t/w = 1p
Cabbage		33 Soya bean products	≥1-3 t/w = 1p
11 Cauliflower	≥1-3 t/w = 1p	Dairy products	
12 Broccoli	≥1-3 t/w = 1p	34 Unpasteurized milk	If yes = 1p
13 White cabbage	≥1-3 t/w = 1p	35 Cow's milk	≥2 dl/day = 1p
Green vegetables		36 Milk replacement	≥2 dl/day = 1p
14 Lettuce	≥1-3 t/w = 1p	37 Soured milk unsweetened	≥1-3 t/w = 1p
15 Avocado	≥1-3 t/w = 1p	38 Yoghurt unsweetened	≥1-3 t/w = 1p
16 Cucumber	≥1-3 t/w = 1p	39 Quark/cottage cheese	≥1-3 t/w = 1p
Other vegetables		40 Nuts, all	≥1-3 t/w = 1p
17 Frozen vegetables	≥1-3 t/w = 1p	→ DD-score	Min 0p, Max 40p
18 Sweet pepper	≥1-3 t/w = 1p		
19 Tomatoes	≥1-3 t/w = 1p		
20 Corn	≥1-3 t/w = 1p		
21 Onion	≥1-3 t/w = 1p		
22 Garlic	≥1-3 t/w = 1p		
23 Mushroom	≥1-3 t/w = 1p		

^a If ranked as the most common type of consumed bread (1 or 2 on a ranking scale of maximum 6) = 1p
t/w, times/week; p, points; DD, diet diversity

Table 2. Percent of 3200 pregnant women reporting each frequency of consumption or mean intake of food items included in a diet diversity (DD) score in pregnancy week 35 ^a

Food items in DD score ^b	Less than 1t/w or never	1-3 t/w	4-6 t/w	1-2 t/d	≥3 t/d
All fruits	1.9	14.8	25.2	46.2	11.9
Tomatoes	4.9	53.7	33.7	7.4	0.4
Beef ^c	6.8	53.8	23.3	5.3	0.1
Boiled potatoes	9.2	75.8	13.6	1.3	0.0
Cucumber	9.6	53.8	25.5	10.5	0.6
Onion	10.6	46.5	35.0	7.7	0.3
Lettuce	12.3	54.6	23.4	9.2	0.5
Chicken ^c	15.8	67.5	5.2	0.7	0.0
Pork ^c	15.5	65.8	7.0	0.8	0.0
Garlic	16.6	51.2	26.8	5.3	0.1
Carrots	16.0	61.2	18.8	3.6	0.4
All berries	20.6	49.2	17.0	12.9	0.4
Egg	24.8	59.8	10.4	4.9	0.2
Sweet pepper	30.2	55.9	11.0	2.8	0.1
Fiber cereals	34.9	32.6	17.3	15.2	0.1
Fatty fish	34.1	64.4	1.2	0.2	0.1
Soured milk (unsweetened)	39.9	27.0	16.5	16.5	0.0
Broccoli	42.2	51.9	5.6	0.3	0.1
Fiber porridge	44.1	38.7	9.8	7.4	0.1
Frozen vegetables	49.1	43.2	6.7	0.9	0.1
Pulses	49.4	39.7	9.5	1.3	0.1
Avocado	49.8	45.6	3.9	0.7	0.0
Mushrooms	51.9	46.0	2.0	0.1	0.0
Corn	53.2	43.3	3.1	0.3	0.1
Lean fish	55.4	43.9	0.5	0.1	0.1
Game ^c	60.3	24.0	4.3	0.5	0.1
Yoghurt (unsweetened)	62.9	23.8	6.8	6.5	0.1
Root vegetables	65.3	32.8	1.8	0.0	0.1
Fiber pasta	69.1	27.1	3.5	0.3	0.1
White cabbage	70.0	26.6	2.9	0.4	0.0
Bulgur, couscous, grains	72.4	26.7	0.9	0.0	0.0
Blood meal ^c	73.4	15.3	0.4	0.0	0.0
Almond	74.0	21.6	2.7	1.4	0.2
Cashew	75.8	21.6	1.9	0.7	0.1
Cauliflower	77.4	21.6	0.8	0.0	0.1
Soya bean products	80.5	15.6	2.7	1.1	0.12
Peanuts	80.4	17.6	1.3	0.5	0.2
Shellfish	81.9	17.9	0.2	0.0	0.0
Probiotic products (fermented)	82.5	11.8	2.6	2.9	0.2
Walnut	84.3	13.1	1.7	1.0	0.1
Lamb ^c	84.9	4.0	0.2	0.0	0.1
Other bird ^c	86.4	2.5	0.4	0-0	0.0
Quark/cottage cheese	87.8	9.5	1.7	1.0	0.1
Hazelnut	88.0	10.4	1.0	0.5	0.1
Brown rice	90.4	9.3	0.3	0.1	0.0
Pistachio	94.2	5.6	0.2	0.0	0.0
Other nuts	95.3	4.1	0.4	0.2	0.0
Milk ^d	Mean (S D)	n			
Cow's milk 3%, dl/d	3.2 (3.4)	370			
Cow's milk 1.5%, dl/d	2.6 (2.2)	2023			
Cow's milk 0.5%, dl/d	3.0 (2.1)	334			
Milk replacement, dl/d	2.1 (1.3)	278			
Milk from farm, dl/d	6.2 (4.0)	11			
Never drink milk or milk	-	184			
Bread	Mean				
Fiber rich soft bread, slices/d ^d	2.5 (1.3)	2231			
Fiber rich crisp bread, slices/ ^d	2.5 (1.4)	1963			

^a Construction and calculation of the DD-score is presented in Table 1

^b Listed food items are all included in the DD score, either as separate food items for the following foods merged as one item: red meat (beef, pork, game, lamb), white meat (chicken, other bird), nuts (almond, cashew, peanuts, walnuts, hazelnuts, pistachio, other nuts)

^c 10.8 % of the participants reported to not eat meat and were thus not asked to report the frequency of this food item

^d Frequency is only based on those participants that ranked fiber rich bread as 1st or 2nd most common type of consumed bread, the rest were omitted in reporting frequency of consumed bread.

d, day; dl, deciliter; SD, standard deviation; t. times; w, week;

Table 3. Association between diet diversity score in pregnancy and cumulative incidence of allergic manifestations until the age of 18 months (n=3200) presenting a sensitivity analysis in addition to the crude and multivariable model presented in the research letter. Odds ratio (OR) and 95% confidence interval (CI) presented per 1 unit increase in diet diversity score.

Outcome	Crude ^a			Multivariable ^b			Sensitivity analysis ^c		
	n cases/total	OR (95%CI)	P	n cases/total	OR (95%CI)	P	n cases/total	OR (95%CI)	P
Eczema	1144/3192	1.00 (0.99-1.02)	0.862	1028/2882	0.99 (0.98-1.01)	0.621	854/2318	1.00 (0.98-1.01)	0.586
Poem 0-7 ^d	974/3192	1.01 (0.99-1.02)	0.717	872/2882	1.00 (0.98-1.02)	0.823	731/2318	1.00 (0.98-1.02)	0.885
Poem 8-28 ^d	170/3192	0.99 (0.96-1.03)	0.637	153/2882	0.98 (0.95-1.02)	0.408	123/2318	0.97 (0.93-1.01)	0.156
Wheeze	620/3075	0.97 (0.96-0.99)	0.009	558/2939	0.98 (0.96-1.00)	0.115	468/2318	0.99 (0.97-1.02)	0.551
Asthma	120/3075	0.99 (0.96-1.04)	0.786	103/2791	1.00 (0.95-1.04)	0.884	81/2318	1.01 (0.96-1.07)	0.634
Food allergy	168/3006	0.96 (0.93-1.00)	0.037	150/2738	0.96 (0.92-0.99)	0.022	128/2318	0.96 (0.92-1.00)	0.038
Positive to Foodmix ^e	338/1922	0.99 (0.97-1.02)	0.616	306/1764	1.00 (0.98-1.04)	0.659	262/1538	1.01 (0.98-1.04)	0.722
Positive to cod ^e	6/1922	0.85 (0.72-1.01)	0.064	6/1764	0.89 (0.75-1.07)	0.207	6/1538	0.83 (0.64-1.09)	0.189
Positive to peanut ^e	63/1922	1.01 (0.95-1.07)	0.777	58/1764	1.01 (0.95-1.07)	0.786	48/1538	1.00 (0.93-1.07)	0.917
Positive to soybean ^e	36/1922	0.96 (0.89-1.03)	0.264	33/1764	0.95 (0.88-1.03)	0.212	28/1538	0.92 (0.84-1.00)	0.058
Positive to cow's milk ^e	203/1922	0.99 (0.96-1.02)	0.514	168/1764	1.00 (0.96-1.03)	0.890	161/1538	1.00 (0.96-1.04)	0.905
Positive to egg ^e	167/1922	1.01 (0.98-1.05)	0.552	153/1764	1.02 (0.98-1.06)	0.386	126/1538	1.01 (0.97-1.06)	0.444
Positive to wheat ^e	55/1922	1.01 (0.96-1.08)	0.644	48/1764	1.02 (0.96-1.09)	0.553	42/1538	1.03 (0.96-1.10)	0.436
Positive to Phadiatop ^e	88/1922	1.02 (0.97-1.07)	0.372	82/1764	1.02 (0.97-1.08)	0.349	68/1538	1.01 (0.96-1.07)	0.628

^a Crude model: energy adjusted DD-score.

^b Multivariable model: adjusted for maternal history of allergy and asthma, maternal education (9y elementary school/gymnasium/academic education), maternal BMI at pregnancy, gestational supplementation, delivery mode, child sex.

^c Sensitivity analysis was additionally adjusted for breastfeeding duration until 18 months of age, child sex (female/male), siblings (yes/no), time for introduction of solid foods until 9 months (<6months/>6 months or not introduced), and probiotic supplementation in infancy (at 4 and 9 months respectively).

^d Multinomial logistic regression with 'no eczema' as reference and eczema in two categories: clear to mild eczema (POEM-score 0-7p) and moderate to severe eczema (POEM-score 8-28p).

^e Sensitization was defined as positive if IgE levels ≥ 0.35 kU/L. Only positive tests from the foodmix were tested for separate food allergen cod, peanut, soybean, cow's milk, egg, and wheat.

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